

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CHOICE OF TREATMENT METHOD FOR DEFECTS OF HARD TISSUES OF THE CROWNS OF VITAL TEETH

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Abstract

The earliest and most common form of damage to the dental system is defects in the hard tissues of the crowns of vital teeth. The causes may be caries, acute and chronic trauma, hypoplasia, fluorosis, wedge-shaped defects, pathological abrasion, congenital and hereditary malformations of hard dental tissues, etc. Each previous pathology is a predisposing factor for the occurrence and development of more severe subsequent pathology.

Keywords; restorations with inlays, crowns.

The tooth as an organ has a typical structure and functions. Each group of teeth is unique. The front teeth have aesthetic, tearing, biting and grasping functions. Chewing teeth are involved in grinding, chewing and grinding food and forming a food bolus. In accordance with the type of pathological changes in teeth and taking into account their affiliation, dentists develop treatment principles, on the basis of which numerous methods and techniques are used. The branch of dentistry associated with the preparation of hard tissues of dental crowns is constantly developing, treatment principles are being revised, new approaches and tactics are being developed, and outdated treatment methods are becoming obsolete. Violations of the integrity of hard tissues of dental crowns (98% according to WHO) have a carious etiology or are associated with the therapeutic effect of the dentist during tooth preparation. According to Academician of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences V.K. Leontiev, the previously significant Black axiom on the expansive principle of surgical excision of hard tissues of dental crowns requires serious revision. The use of new classes of synthetic materials - composites, glass ionomers, compomers, ceramers, adhesive systems and cushioning materials allows us to move from the principle of preventive excision of hard tissues of dental crowns to the principle of their maximum preservation. Based on the foregoing, it is important to formulate adequate principles and approaches to the treatment of teeth when treating them with new filling materials. It is necessary to take into account the type, shape, depth and degree of carious lesions, the possibility of maximizing the preservation of hard tooth tissues and preventing the development of secondary caries. Chief dentist of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation, academician of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences Leontiev V.K. notes the need to develop, based on scientific research, clear indications and contraindications for the use of individual materials, depending on the nature of the carious lesion, the possibilities and conditions of treatment.

These principles should be taught in universities and in the postgraduate education system. They should be prescribed in treatment standards [1]. Classifications of lesions have important theoretical and practical significance from the point of view of a differentiated approach to the technique and method of treating hard tissues of dental crowns. Lesions are classified: by location (G. Black, B.N. Bynin, D.N. Tsitrin, B. Boyanov); on topography (T.V. Sharova, Balters, ICD-DA, 1994 WHO, A.Z. Petrikas); by area of damage (V.Yu. Milikevich, T.F. Danilina); by the length of the defect (Klaiber, 1992). Some classifications are accompanied by recommendations for treatment methods. The most popular among dentists in this matter is the classification proposed by V.Yu. Milikevich (1984). Using it, the doctor, having assessed the area of damage to the occlusal surface, can determine the method of treatment. It is also necessary to remember that the area of damage to the hard tissues of the tooth crown before preparation may differ greatly from that after preparation. Therefore, this method of determining the area of the defect does not always provide a complete clinical picture of the spread of the pathological process and, as a result, problems arise with the correctness of the chosen treatment method. Dentists are actively discussing the limits of maximum intervention in the preparation of hard tissues of the crowns of vital teeth for direct restoration with composites. No less relevant is the issue of minimum preparation. The values are fixed by a stopper, freely moved along the graduated part of the instrument and determined using a ruler. The ratio of the obtained values gives us the index of the depth of destruction of the tooth crown (IGRKZ). Based on the results of clinical and experimental studies using the method described above, the mathematical finite element method and data obtained at a clinical appointment, we have compiled a table with recommendations on the tactics and method of treating a defect in the hard tissues of the crown of a vital tooth, taking into account

the area and depth of the lesion. The range of possibilities for using the filling method is limited by the values of IROPP = 0.4 and IGRKZ = 0.4, starting from the values of IROPP = 0.5 and IGRKZ = 0.5, the method of choice for treating a defect in the hard tissues of the crown of a vital tooth is an inlay. Using this method, 920 patients aged 11 to 57 years (573 women and 347 men, of which 83 children aged 11 to 17 years) who applied for defects in the hard tissues of the crowns of vital teeth were treated. To carry out all types of aesthetic restorations at the preparation stage, we used the principles of minimal surgical intervention in the hard tissues of the crown of a vital tooth. The quality of the preparation was assessed using a caries indicator. The results of immediate and long-term observations carried out over a period of 1 month to 5 years showed the high efficiency of the proposed method. During the clinical examination, the quality of the restorations performed was assessed according to FDA criteria. Based on the results of the treatment, there was a tendency to increase the range of indications for the treatment of volumetric defects in the hard tissues of the crowns of vital teeth with inlays made of modern aesthetic materials. Restorations carried out with inlays made of composite materials, made by indirect and direct clinical methods for children over the age of 11 years, allow us to recommend this type of treatment as a reliable method of prolonging the vital condition of teeth that were previously (up to 70%) subjected to devitalization. Filling cavities with composite materials, taking into account the above-described indices, allows us to guarantee the high efficiency of the restorations carried out, bringing their service life closer to international standards (from 6 to 8 years). The author expresses the hope that the method we propose will find wide application in clinical consultations and will help practicing

dentists to adequately resolve issues regarding the choice of treatment methods in each specific clinical case.

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